

GAIVA: A Generative AI Framework for Human–AI Collaboration in Educational Video Analysis

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Qualitative video analysis is a foundational yet labor-intensive method in the learning sciences, particularly for investigating the multimodal and collaborative dimensions of learning. This paper introduces *GAIVA* (Generative Artificial Intelligence for Video Analysis), a novel framework that integrates multimodal large language models (MLLMs) and large language models (LLMs) to support scalable, consistent, and theory-informed video analysis. *GAIVA* comprises four sequential phases: (1) video preprocessing, (2) MLLM-based behavioral transcription, (3) human–AI collaborative codebook development grounded in theoretical constructs from computer-supported collaborative learning (CSCL), and (4) LLM-based automated coding. Drawing on a case study to analyze simulation-based collaborative science learning, we demonstrate that *GAIVA* generates rich behavioral transcriptions, enables the construction of stable and theoretically grounded coding schemes, and achieves inter-rater reliability comparable to human annotation. Notably, findings illustrate *GAIVA*'s capacity to support both deductive alignment and inductive discovery. The framework surfaces a behavioral construct—*Peripheral Engagement*—that is consistent across data batches but absent from existing frameworks. We contribute a systematic and replicable framework for integrating generative AI into qualitative video research, enabling large-scale, multimodal analysis of collaborative learning while preserving analytical rigor, theoretical coherence, and interpretive transparency.

Keywords: video analysis, generative AI, human–AI collaboration, multimodal large language models, large language models, collaborative learning, qualitative coding, computer-supported collaborative learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Video analysis has long been a foundational method in learning sciences and computer-supported collaborative learning (CSCL) research for investigating the complex interplay of cognitive, social, and embodied dimensions of learning (Derry et al., 2010; Jewitt, 2012). Unlike other forms of data (e.g., log files, discourse transcript, audio data), video preserves the rich interplay of multimodal data: verbal exchanges, embodied actions, gaze attention, and tool use

that characterizes authentic learning processes (Heath et al., 2010; Barron et al., 2012). This richness has enabled researchers to examine learning in context and at multiple levels of granularity, making video a valuable tool for a wide range of studies, including investigations of teacher professional development, classroom orchestration, collaborative problem-solving, and inquiry-based learning (Powell et al., 2003; Hollingsworth, 2005; Calandra and Rich, 2014; Cukurova et al., 2020).

However, the analytical affordance of video comes with significant methodological challenges. Qualitative video analysis is highly time-consuming and labor-intensive, often requiring dozens of hours to analyze just a single hour of footage (Markle et al., 2011; Snell, 2011; Lemke, 2014). In addition, video analysis faces challenges with consistency. Researchers must make decisions about which behaviors to attend to, how to segment video episodes, and how to interpret actions within context. These decisions may vary across researchers or even within the same researcher over time, raising concerns about reliability and replicability (Erickson, 2006; Lemke, 2014). The absence of standardized protocols to guide these choices can lead to reduced transparency and potential cherry-picking of moments that appear compelling but may not be representative of broader patterns (Hammersley, 2010; Blikstad-Balas, 2017). Beyond the challenges of clip selection, segmentation, and transcription, researchers must also decide how to categorize and code behaviors. While pre-established coding frameworks can improve interpretive coherence (Derry et al., 2010), they may overlook context-specific or emergent patterns (Erickson, 2006; Snell, 2011). Taken together, these challenges highlight opportunities to advance video analysis methods that are scalable, consistent, and theoretically and contextually grounded.

Efforts to address these challenges have driven the development of various analytical tools. Early innovations included Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS), which excels at organizing data but does not reduce the core labor of watching and coding footage (Bezemer and Mavers, 2011; Luff and Heath, 2012). Subsequent work explored Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) to streamline discourse transcription, yet these systems are primarily unimodal, struggle with overlapping speech in multi-speaker environments, and cannot capture the rich nonverbal cues central to meaning making (Southwell et al., 2022; Basak et al., 2023). More recently, computer vision and deep learning systems have shown promise in recognizing specific physical actions. However, these systems often rely on extensive labeled datasets and have difficulties generalizing across different populations and contexts, limiting their effectiveness (Foster et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2025).

Recent advances in generative AI (GenAI)—specifically multimodal large language models (MLLMs)—present new opportunities. MLLMs such as Gemini and GPT-4o extend large language models (LLMs) by enabling joint reasoning across textual and visual inputs (Wu et al., 2023). Specifically, video-based MLLMs are designed to process temporally ordered sequences of frames, allowing them to capture how actions unfold over time in zero-shot settings, thereby reducing the need for annotated training data (Huang et al., 2024). However, their application in authentic educational contexts remains largely underexplored. Existing MLLMs are often trained on general-purpose datasets that differ significantly from context-sensitive learning behaviors (Huang et al., 2024; Maaz et al., 2024), raising questions about their reliability and accuracy.

In response to these challenges and opportunities, this paper introduces GAIVA (Generative Artificial Intelligence for Video Analysis), a novel framework designed to integrate MLLMs and LLMs in the video analysis pipeline. While classroom recordings often contain multiple modalities, the current implementation of GAIVA focuses exclusively on the visual stream and does not incorporate audio data. This decision aligns with our analytic focus on nonverbal

collaborative behaviors. GAIVA includes three key phases: behavioral transcription, codebook development, and automated coding. Rather than replacing human researchers, GAIVA employs human-in-the-loop approaches in each phase, leveraging MLLMs for video understanding and LLMs for qualitative coding, while preserving researcher oversight in prompt design, theoretical framing, and output validation. We present a case study using GAIVA to analyze classroom videos of students engaged in collaborative problem solving during a simulation-based science activity. The overarching research question of this study is: to what extent can current GenAI models support scalable, consistent, and theoretically grounded qualitative video analysis? In this context, *consistency* refers to the model’s ability to apply the same analytical criteria across datasets, producing stable and repeatable output for the same video input (Hammersley, 2010; Blikstad-Balas, 2017). *Theoretical alignment* asks whether model output moves beyond surface-level descriptions and can be meaningfully mapped onto established constructs from CSCL (Derry et al., 2010; Zahn et al., 2021). We address the research question through a systematic evaluation of each phase of the GAIVA pipeline, guided by the following sub-questions:

1. How effectively can MLLMs transcribe nonverbal collaborative behaviors, and how does transcription quality vary across different prompt strategies?
2. How does human–AI collaboration support the development of a theoretically grounded qualitative codebook to analyze collaborative learning?
3. How reliably can LLMs apply a human-refined, theory-informed codebook to MLLM-generated behavioral transcriptions for automated coding?

This work makes three primary contributions to the fields of educational data mining and learning sciences. First, we present a systematic, theoretically grounded, and replicable framework for integrating GenAI into qualitative video analysis. We draw from CSCL research in leveraging GenAI to transcribe videos and generate codebooks. Second, it provides empirical insights into the affordances and limitations of GenAI for analyzing complex educational data. Third, it offers practical guidance on prompt engineering and validation strategies to enhance the reliability and transparency of AI-assisted educational research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. ROLE OF VIDEO IN ANALYZING COLLABORATIVE LEARNING

Video has become an essential methodological data source in learning sciences and CSCL research, supporting a wide range of approaches from experimental and quasi-experimental designs to field research and case studies (Derry et al., 2010; Goldman et al., 2014). Its strength lies in its capacity to capture the complex, dynamic nature of learning processes as they unfold in authentic contexts (Barron et al., 2012). In CSCL environments, students coordinate activity and construct shared understanding through verbal exchanges and embodied actions, including gaze, gesture, posture, spatial orientation, and tool use (Kang et al., 2024). These behaviors often unfold across both digital interfaces and physical spaces, forming a rich interaction that is central to collaborative meaning-making but difficult to capture using data sources like log files, chat transcripts, or audio recordings (Martinez-Maldonado et al., 2021; Ochoa, 2022). Video addresses this challenge by preserving the full temporal, spatial, and embodied context of interactions. As Erickson (2011) notes, it enables “a multimodal and multiparty analysis of the locally situated ecological processes of interaction and meaning making” (p. 181). This capability allows researchers to examine what he describes as the “semiotic ecology” of social interaction—how participants use bodily orientation, tool manipulation, and nonverbal cues to

coordinate with others and construct shared meaning. Importantly, video offers analytical flexibility that supports both fine-grained, event-based analysis of key learning moments and sequential process analysis that traces how collaborative learning unfolds over time in response to emergent group dynamics (Zahn et al., 2021).

Empirical studies across CSCL contexts have demonstrated how video reveals the temporal and embodied dimensions of collaboration that are not easy to capture from other data sources. This capacity has enabled researchers to develop theoretical constructs and document subtle collaborative processes across diverse learning settings. For example, the concept of a “joint problem space” emerged from detailed video analysis of student dyads working through physics problems (Roschelle, 1992; Roschelle & Teasley, 1995). Through iterative viewing, researchers identified recurring patterns in which students displayed, confirmed, and repaired understandings through coordinated cycles of embodied gestures, verbal references to screen objects, and strategic alignments of attention. Similarly, Koschmann et al. (2014) used ethnomethodological video analysis to examine collaborative construction of disciplinary reasoning, using narrative methods to reveal the sequential organization of collaborative sense-making. In collaborative programming environments, Campe et al. (2020) used time-stamped video coding to identify distinct interaction patterns. Their analyses highlighted video's value in capturing subtle non-verbal behaviors and shifts in roles or engagement levels that would be missed in log-only or audio-only approaches.

These studies collectively highlight video as a data source that enables the detailed, multi-modal analysis necessary to understand how collaborative learning emerges through the dynamic interplay of verbal discourse, embodied action, and material engagement. As learning environments become increasingly complex and technologically mediated, video's capacity to preserve and analyze the full spectrum of collaborative activity makes it an indispensable component of CSCL research.

2.2. MLLMs IN EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH

MLLMs extend the capabilities of unimodal architectures by integrating vision encoders within LLMs to process multimodal inputs (e.g., text, image, video) and generate contextualized outputs (Wu et al., 2023; Yin et al., 2024). A core innovation in MLLMs is cross-modal attention (Lu et al., 2019), a mechanism that enables models to dynamically integrate and relate textual and visual information, thereby enhancing their ability to infer meaning from multimodal data. Recent research has begun to explore the application of MLLMs in education. Xing et al. (2024) identified four major application areas where MLLMs are being deployed: adaptive learning platforms, automated content generation, assessment and grading, and student learning analytics. For example, Nguyen and Hayward (2025) examined how MLLMs could evaluate the quality of science assessment that combines student-written and diagrammatic responses. The models demonstrated the potential for analyses at scale, as they successfully interpreted both visual and textual features of different assessments across science domains and grade levels.

More directly relevant to video-based research, researchers have started to explore how MLLMs can support the analysis of non-verbal and embodied dimensions of learning. Whitehead et al. (2025) leveraged GPT-4o to extract postural features relevant to socially shared regulation of learning in collaborative settings. Their case study proposed a structured workflow for using MLLMs to identify postural indicators of engagement and coordination, evaluating both test–retest reliability and alignment with human coding. While the model produced consistent outputs, agreement with human annotations varied across posture categories, highlighting the need for careful validation. Similarly, Zhou et al. (2025) examined the risk of

hallucinations in MLLM-generated behavior descriptions in education. They found that even when surface-level actions were correctly recognized, models might misattribute roles or over-interpret interactions. While prior work has demonstrated the value of MLLMs for analyzing non-verbal cues and supporting various educational tasks, their use as end-to-end analytical tools for qualitative video analysis in CSCL remains underexplored. We address this gap by systematically examining how MLLMs can be used to transcribe, interpret, and classify collaborative interactions in authentic classroom video data.

2.3. AFFORDANCES OF VIDEO-BASED MLLMS

Video-based MLLMs offer several important capabilities that make them particularly well-suited for analyzing collaborative learning processes. These include zero-shot learning, multimodal processing, temporal reasoning, and the generation of natural language outputs. One key affordance is **zero-shot learning**—the ability of a model to perform new tasks without being explicitly trained on them. Traditional supervised models require researchers to manually annotate thousands of behavioral instances to create training datasets. This process is both time-consuming and resource-intensive (Liu et al., 2025). MLLMs, by contrast, are trained on large-scale, diverse datasets and can apply their learned representations to new tasks without task-specific fine-tuning (Brown et al., 2020). This allows researchers to analyze novel educational scenarios without additional training, reducing dependence on labeled datasets and supporting rapid prototyping in real-world contexts. Another advantage is **multimodal processing**. Unlike traditional computer vision models, which often rely solely on pixel-based representations and can misclassify visually similar behaviors due to limited contextual awareness (Feichtenhofer et al., 2019), MLLMs integrate both visual and textual information. Using mechanisms such as cross-modal attention (Lu et al., 2019), MLLMs can relate visual cues to semantic prompts, allowing for more context-aware interpretations of student behavior.

A third key affordance is **temporal reasoning**. Unlike image-based models such as GPT-4V (OpenAI, 2024), which interpret each frame independently, video-based MLLMs (e.g., LLaVA-Video, Flamingo, Video-ChatGPT) are designed to process sequences of frames (Alayrac et al., 2022; Maaz et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). This enables them to track how behaviors unfold over time, which is essential for interpreting classroom actions that depend on timing and context. For instance, distinguishing whether a raised hand indicates participation, stretching, or a social signal depends on observing how the action evolves within its interactional context (Xu et al., 2021). This temporal understanding supports more accurate interpretation of behaviors.

Finally, **natural language generation** enhances the transparency and usability of MLLMs in educational settings. Traditional machine learning models often operate as "black boxes," providing classifications without transparent reasoning (Wang et al., 2023). In contrast, MLLMs can generate descriptive summaries and provide textual explanations for their outputs (Alayrac et al., 2022). This supports researcher interpretation by offering insight into why certain behaviors were identified and how they were described. This capability provides additional insights beyond binary classification and serves as a bridge between raw video footage and human analysis. Unlike low-level feature pipelines that require additional processing to derive meaning, MLLMs offer outputs that are directly usable for qualitative coding and interpretation.

While these affordances show promise for educational video analysis, MLLMs do not automatically resolve foundational methodological concerns central to rigorous qualitative research, such as scalability (Lemke, 2014), consistency (Hammersley, 2010), and theoretical alignment (Derry et al., 2010). These considerations inform our creation and evaluation of GAIVA.

3. METHODS

3.1. CONTEXT AND PARTICIPANTS

The study was conducted using HoloOrbits, an immersive learning environment designed to teach planetary motion and orbital mechanics. This platform enables students to collaborate in exploring planetary systems, visualize elliptical orbits, and collect data such as distances between celestial objects to analyze orbital systems. Participants utilized the laptop version (WebGL) as shown in Figure 1 with screen-based interactions.

Figure 1: Simulated exoplanetary system in HoloOrbits.

Figure 2: Video recordings from WebGL session with a group-centered camera angle.

A total of 24 undergraduate students from Midwestern University participated in the research, working in groups of 2 to 3 students as shown in Figure 2. Due to data availability and consent to record video recordings, thirteen students forming five groups were included in the final analysis. While this represents a subset of the total sample, it provides sufficient data to validate our AI-assisted video analysis pipeline across different collaborative configurations. The sample comprised five distinct groups with varying compositions: three groups of three students (one all-male, one with 1 female and 2 males, one with 2 females and 1 male) and two groups of two students (one all-male, one mixed gender). This diversity in group size and gender composition captured a range of collaborative dynamics that naturally occur in classroom settings.

Sessions followed a standardized structure lasting approximately one hour and thirty minutes. Each session began with a pre-survey and platform tutorial, followed by structured collaborative problem-solving tasks where students learned planetary motion and Kepler's laws within the simulation. Students began with a hands-on paper-based activity to construct and label an elliptical orbit, which served as a conceptual foundation for the simulation. Then, using the measurement tools in HoloOrbits, groups collaborated to plan data collection strategies, observe orbital behavior, and interpret distance measurements to determine whether the simulated planetary system followed Kepler's first law. The sessions concluded with a post-survey and debrief discussion for participant reflection. All procedures received institutional review board approval to ensure ethical compliance.

3.2. VIDEO CORPUS

We collected five video recordings from two classroom sessions. The recordings captured collaborative learning interactions as students engaged in the group problem-solving tasks. Each recording documented approximately 33 minutes of classroom activity, beginning after introductory instructions and ending before post-task questionnaires. Four recordings employed a group-centered camera angle positioned to capture all group members' faces, gestures, and shared materials simultaneously. One recording used a side-view angle due to classroom spatial constraints, which still maintained visibility of key nonverbal behaviors including gaze patterns and body orientation (see Figure 3). All recordings were collected with informed participant consent.

Figure 3: Examples of camera perspectives: group-centered (left), side-view (right).

4. GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR VIDEO ANALYSIS (GAIVA)

To address persistent challenges in qualitative video analysis—including its time-intensive nature, inconsistency in interpretation, and limited theoretical grounding—this paper introduces GAIVA (Generative Artificial Intelligence for Video Analysis), a novel four-phase framework that integrates MLLMs and LLMs into the video analysis pipeline. GAIVA is designed to support scalable, consistent, and theory-informed analysis of classroom video through a structured, human–AI collaboration process. We present GAIVA through a case study, where we analyzed classroom recordings of students engaged in collaborative problem-solving using a simulation-based science activity.

Figure 4: Workflow of GAIVA framework.

The framework consists of four sequential phases: (1) video preprocessing, (2) behavioral transcription using MLLMs, (3) theory-informed codebook development through human–AI collaboration, and (4) automated coding using LLMs. This sequence was designed to mirror the analytic progression of qualitative video analysis: researchers first prepare and segment video data, then produce descriptions of observable activity, then develop interpretive categories, and finally apply those categories systematically across the corpus. Phases 1 and 2 leverage MLLMs to generate fine-grained transcriptions of nonverbal behaviors directly from video data, supported by iterative prompt optimization. Phases 3 and 4 rely on text-only LLMs to generate theory-aligned behavioral codes and apply them at scale across transcripts. The use of different model types is therefore tied to the analytic function of each phase, rather than to a claim that one model type is universally superior to the other. In this workflow, MLLMs are used for tasks that require processing visual input, namely, generating descriptions of observable behaviors from video data (Phase 2). Text-only LLMs are then used for code generation and classification (Phases 3 and 4). This design was informed by prior work suggesting that multimodal processing

may introduce additional challenges for extended reasoning and structured interpretation tasks, partly due to the computational demands associated with processing high-dimensional visual inputs (Lu et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2023; Yin et al., 2024). Separating behavioral transcription from code generation also makes the analytic process more inspectable. In particular, MLLM-generated behavioral transcripts allow researchers to review the video-to-text representation before downstream coding and to examine whether potential problems appear to originate from the transcription stage or the subsequent code-application stage. At the same time, researchers should be cautious not to assume that a staged structure inherently reduces measurement error, as inaccuracies introduced in earlier phases may still propagate through later stages without additional validation.

4.1. PHASE 1: VIDEO PROCESSING AND MODEL CONFIGURATION

We standardized video files to consistent resolution and encoding formats to ensure uniform processing across the dataset. We preserved audio data but did not utilize them in the current analysis, which focused exclusively on visual nonverbal behaviors. We segmented videos into non-overlapping 10-second clips and sampled at 2 frames per second (fps), yielding 20 frames per segment. These parameters were informed by our previous research (Zhou et al., 2025) and pilot analysis of collaborative learning behaviors. Typical collaborative behaviors in our dataset unfold within 3-8 second intervals, making 10-second segments long enough to capture complete behavioral units while minimizing the likelihood of including multiple distinct behavioral states within a single clip. The 2fps sampling rate provided adequate temporal resolution to detect key nonverbal behaviors, including gaze shifts, gestures, and posture changes, while maintaining computational efficiency. Our pilot testing revealed that increasing the sampling rate to 4 and 8 fps approximately tripled the processing time and tokens, while yielding negligible improvements in detecting these coarse-grained behaviors. Although the model can capture momentary changes, most target behaviors in our dataset (e.g., gaze shifts, gestures, posture changes) unfold over several seconds. As a result, sampling more densely mainly adds near-identical frames, increasing computational cost without contributing substantively new behavioral information. We note that these processing parameters are tailored to the temporal characteristics of our dataset and instructional setting, and may require adjustment in other learning contexts where behaviors differ in granularity or temporal scale.

We conducted model inference using the pre-trained LLaVA-Video-72B-Qwen2 model (shortened as LLaVA), a state-of-the-art vision-language model capable of temporal video understanding and multimodal reasoning (Zhang et al., 2024). Built on the Qwen2 architecture, this model integrates frame-level visual encoders with a transformer-based language model to process temporally ordered sequences of images alongside natural language prompts. This architecture allows LLaVA to reason over dynamic visual input, making it particularly well-suited for identifying and describing classroom behaviors that unfold over time, such as gaze shifts, gestures, and peer interactions.

We selected LLaVA for three key reasons. First, it is publicly available and fully open-source, ensuring reproducibility and avoiding reliance on commercial APIs or cloud services that may limit privacy or scalability. Second, LLaVA has been trained on large-scale datasets and benchmarked on standard video-language tasks such as action recognition and temporal localization, demonstrating competitive performance across multiple domains (Fu et al., 2024; Yin et al., 2024). Third, its widespread adoption and active community support make it a useful model for comparative studies and real-world educational applications.

We did not fine-tune the model for both practical and conceptual reasons. Practically, our dataset of five recordings is insufficient for effective model fine-tuning, which typically requires hundreds or thousands of training examples. Conceptually, using pre-trained models assesses the model's inherent capabilities to interpret classroom interactions and provides baseline performance insights for researchers applying similar models to new educational contexts without domain-specific training. We set the model's temperature to 0 to ensure consistent and reproducible model outputs. All video processing and model inference were performed on the FASTER cluster using three NVIDIA A100 GPUs with 40GB memory each.

4.2. PHASE 2: MLLM PROMPT SELECTION AND VIDEO TRANSCRIPTION

This phase employed LLaVA to generate detailed behavioral descriptions from classroom video recordings. The process involved systematic prompt engineering to evaluate different prompting strategies, followed by empirical assessment to select the most effective approach for transcription quality.

4.2.1. Prompt Engineering

To systematically select the prompt leading to highest-quality LLaVA-generated behavior descriptions, we implemented a structured prompt engineering protocol. The strategy for developing effective prompts involved an iterative process of refinement to align model responses with the task requirements. These prompt engineering strategies were selected based on their demonstrated effectiveness in LLMs (Chen et al., 2024; Nguyen and Hayward, 2025; Sahoo et al., 2024) and potential applicability to MLLM applications. While few-shot prompting has proven effective, we excluded it due to two considerations. First, our goal was to assess LLaVA's inherent capabilities without biasing responses toward specific example patterns. Prior research indicates that few-shot examples can lead to overgeneralization or overlearning from the provided examples (Liu et al., 2024). Second, relying on human-written transcriptions for few-shot prompting is not always feasible. From a cost and efficiency standpoint, our approach allows other researchers to follow the same pipeline for video analysis.

All prompts shared a consistent core task description to ensure fair comparison: "Describe the interactions between students in detail, focusing on specific gaze patterns, attention shifts, body language, and observable behaviors that signal attention, engagement, or collaboration. Provide concrete examples from the video and indicate how these behaviors reflect the students' level of focus or interaction with peers." We then augmented this baseline task description with different prompt strategies to create five prompts (Table 1).

Table 1: Prompt engineering strategies and specific prompts.

Prompt engineering strategy	Prompt
Zero-shot	[Task description]
Role-assignment	Act as an educational researcher specializing in qualitative analysis and ethnographic video analysis, with a focus on interpreting non-verbal behavioral cues and group dynamics in educational settings. + [Task description]
Tone-adjusted	Use clear and descriptive language to produce detailed, structured observations suitable for behavioral coding, avoiding

Prompt engineering strategy	Prompt
	vague or overly interpretive phrasing unless explicitly supported by evidence. + [Task description]
Context	This is a classroom recording where a group of undergraduate students work on collaborative problem-solving tasks to learn Kepler’s laws. The students engage in pen-and-paper activities or individual laptops to run simulations. The facilitators observe the process, occasionally intervening to answer questions. + [Task description]
Chain of thought (CoT)	First, observe and describe individual student behaviors. Next, analyze and describe the interactions between students in detail. Finally, summarize recurring behavioral patterns. + [Task description]

4.2.2. Prompt Evaluation and Selection

To compare how different prompting strategies shaped the quality of generated behavioral transcripts, we tested all five strategies on a sample of 50 randomly selected video segments, generating 250 total outputs for evaluation (see Appendix 1 for examples of the LLaVA generated outputs). Each output was assessed using a multi-dimensional scoring rubric (see Table 2), including three dimensions: *accuracy*, *completeness*, and *specificity*. The rubric was used to compare prompt strategies at the transcript level, with attention to the accuracy, completeness, and specificity of the transcript as a whole. These dimensions were grounded in prior work on evaluating video transcriptions and AI-generated outputs in educational settings (Bezemer and Mavers, 2011; Baig and Yadegaridehkordi, 2024; Nguyen and Hayward, 2025; Steiss et al., 2024; Yusuf et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2025). The research team initially drafted the rubric based on this literature search, then refined it through two iterative rounds of discussion and pilot coding to ensure operational clarity. The finalized rubric guidelines were provided to coders to ensure consistent application.

Accuracy evaluated the factual correctness of student behavioral descriptions and their fidelity to the task prompt. For this evaluation, relevance at the transcription stage was defined in relation to the task focus: observable student interaction behaviors, including gaze patterns, attention shifts, body language, and peer interaction. Coders evaluated whether these concrete behavioral descriptions were supported by observable evidence in the corresponding video segment. Information outside this task focus, such as classroom layout, furniture, or surrounding objects, were treated as extraneous to the transcription goal, while recognizing that such details may be relevant for other forms of educational video analysis.

Within this scope, the accuracy rubric therefore examined whether the model correctly described the targeted student interaction behaviors and whether it introduced additional information outside the transcription focus. The evaluation focused on observable behavioral descriptions rather than inferred psychological or interpretive constructs, such as engagement, motivation, attention, or collaboration quality. By focusing on visible evidence, the rubric allowed coders to assess both factual grounding and task alignment. This was important because hallucinations in MMLM-generated outputs can involve content extraneous to the task context (Zhou et al., 2025). Previous research has emphasized that ensuring factual accuracy is a critical prerequisite for establishing the trustworthiness of AI-generated content, particularly in

educational contexts where such outputs may inform teacher judgments, research insights, or real-time interventions (Baig and Yadegaridehkordi, 2024; Nguyen and Hayward, 2025; Yusuf et al., 2024). Accuracy was rated on a 5-point ordinal scale ranging from hallucinated or incorrect behavioral descriptions to fully accurate, task-focused descriptions. Importantly, any inaccuracies in relevant student interaction behaviors were treated as core behavioral errors. When relevant behaviors were described accurately, higher scores distinguished whether extraneous information was inaccurate, accurate though unnecessary, or absent altogether.

Completeness assessed the breadth of behavioral coverage in the generated descriptions, as collaboration interactions are inherently multidimensional and span across verbal, visual, and embodied channels (Martinez-Maldonado et al., 2019; Chejara, 2020; Zhou and Kang, 2023). Outputs were rated on a 4-point scale, ranging from covering only one core behavioral aspect (score 1) to capturing all three core aspects plus additional relevant indicators (score 4).

Specificity measured how well claims were grounded in observable evidence, addressing concerns that GenAI models can produce overgeneralized or superficially plausible statements that lack grounding in the input data (Banihashem et al., 2024; Steiss et al., 2024). For instance, stating "the student was engaged" lacks clarity unless supported by specific actions like "the student leaned forward and pointed at the worksheet." Ratings followed a 4-point scale, with highest scores reflecting more consistent use of concrete supporting details.

Table 2: Scoring rubric for video transcription.

Dimension	Score	Standard
Accuracy	1	Core Behavioral Errors Output contains fundamental errors in describing or interpreting <i>relevant</i> student behaviors and interactions.
	2	Relevant Behaviors Correct, High Irrelevant Errors Relevant behaviors are described correctly, but output includes significant inaccuracies (>50%) in <i>irrelevant</i> information.
	3	Relevant Behaviors Correct, Some Irrelevant Errors Relevant behaviors are described correctly, with some inaccuracies (<50%) in <i>irrelevant</i> information.
	4	Fully Accurate (Includes Irrelevant) Both relevant student behaviors <i>and</i> any irrelevant information generated are described correctly.
	5	Fully Accurate (Only Relevant) Output contains <i>only</i> accurate descriptions of <i>relevant</i> student behaviors and interactions; no irrelevant information is generated.
Completeness	1	Minimal Coverage Output describes behaviors related to only ONE of the following core aspects: Gaze/Visual Attention, Hand Gestures/Body Language, or Peer Interaction/Attention Shifts.
	2	Partial Coverage Output describes behaviors across TWO of the three core behavioral aspects listed above.

Dimension	Score	Standard
	3	Core Coverage Output comprehensively describes behaviors across ALL THREE core behavioral aspects: Gaze/Visual Attention, Hand Gestures/Body Language, and Peer Interaction/Attention Shifts.
	4	Comprehensive Coverage Output comprehensively describes behaviors across all three core behavioral aspects and includes descriptions of ADDITIONAL behaviors that signal attention, engagement, or collaboration.
Specificity	1	Vague, No Evidence General behavioral statements are made with NO specific observable evidence or supporting details provided.
	2	Limited Evidence General behavioral statements are supported by AT LEAST ONE, but typically only one, specific observable evidence sentence/detail per described behavioral aspect.
	3	Moderate Evidence Most significant general behavioral statements are supported by AT LEAST TWO specific observable evidence sentences/details per described behavioral aspect.
	4	High Evidence ALL significant general behavioral statements are strongly supported by AT LEAST TWO specific observable evidence sentences/details each.

Two researchers independently scored the 250 outputs (50 segments \times 5 prompts) using the rubric. Inter-rater reliability was established through an initial double-coded subset ($n=50$), with discrepancies resolved through discussion focused on rubric interpretation. To mitigate potential confirmation bias, coders evaluated whether claims in the transcripts were supported by observable evidence in the video, rather than searching for expected or predefined behaviors. After social moderation, we achieved 96.7% exact agreement for accuracy (100% within 1-point, ICC = 0.99), 90% exact agreement for completeness (100% within 1-point, ICC = 0.89), and 93.3% exact agreement for specificity (100% within 1-point, ICC = 0.93). These results indicate that raters were able to apply the transcript-level rubric consistently. After achieving high inter-rater alignment, one researcher scored the remaining 200 outputs (40 video segments \times 5 prompt strategies), yielding a total of 250 evaluated transcriptions. Following this evaluation, the best-performing prompt strategy was applied to generate behavioral descriptions for all video segments in the complete dataset.

4.3. PHASE 3: HUMAN–AI CODEBOOK DEVELOPMENT

This phase employed an iterative, human–AI collaborative approach to develop a theoretically grounded codebook for analyzing student non-verbal interactions. The goal was to transform the detailed behavioral descriptions generated by LLaVA into higher-level constructs that captured the nature and quality of student collaboration. Because the input to this phase consisted of MLLM-generated descriptions of observable nonverbal collaborative behaviors, the resulting

codebook was developed to characterize collaboration within that analytic scope rather than representing all dimensions of classroom interaction. The resulting constructs moved beyond low-level behavioral observations to capture broader, meaningful patterns of collaboration.

4.3.1. Preliminary Inductive Coding

We began by reviewing the LLaVA-generated transcriptions of classroom video segments to develop an initial understanding of the nonverbal behaviors captured by the model, including gaze patterns, gestures, attention shifts, and peer interactions. To examine how LLMs might identify behavioral patterns within these descriptions, we conducted preliminary inductive coding using GPT-4o. To ensure deterministic and reproducible outputs, we set the temperature to 0. All other parameters remained at the model's default API values. During this pilot round, we found that the model generated broad engagement categories such as “*low*,” “*medium*,” and “*high interaction*,” as well as behavior-based groupings like “*collaborative engagement*,” “*reflective posture*,” and “*disengaged presence*.” While these labels captured some behavioral variation and were interpretable, they tended to lack theoretical grounding. Prior research also observed this limitation in using LLMs to generate open codes (Barany *et al.*, 2024; Ramanathan *et al.*, 2025). This motivated the development of a theory-guided process to improve the theoretical rigor of the resulting codebook.

4.3.2. Theory-Guided Codebook Refinement

Given that codebooks from inductive coding lacked grounding in established educational theory, we developed a procedure that combined inductive coding with theoretical alignment, drawing on recent methodological advances in AI-assisted qualitative analysis (Barany *et al.*, 2024; Chen *et al.*, 2024; Liu *et al.*, 2024; Zhou *et al.*, 2025). We treated prompt design as a mechanism for embedding theory into the LLM-assisted coding process (Ramanathan *et al.*, 2025). Specifically, we introduced education theories by providing references in the prompt. We selected GPT-4o for codebook generation based on comparative testing using a random 5% of the data. We evaluated GPT-4o against Gemini 2.5 (a leading proprietary alternative at the time of this research) and Llama-3-70B-Instruct (a leading open-source alternative) using identical prompts. GPT-4o demonstrated superior capability in theoretical grounding (i.e., explicitly mapping candidate codes to CSCL constructs) and in producing conceptually distinct, educationally meaningful codes rather than broad or overlapping categories. To verify theoretical grounding, we manually examined GPT-4o's rationale and found that it consistently demonstrated familiarity with cited papers by referencing key concepts from the theoretical frameworks. We employed a citation-based approach for theory integration and provided references to theoretical frameworks rather than full-text papers. This allowed us to conserve tokens to include more LLaVA-generated descriptions within the model's processing limits (see appendix 2 for final prompt).

We selected Goodwin's embodied participation framework (Goodwin, 2000, 2007) because it conceptualizes interaction as a situated, multimodal process shaped by coordinated use of embodied actions. This conceptualization directly aligns with the nonverbal behaviors captured in our video data and processed by LLaVA. Unlike cognitive frameworks that focus on internal mental states inaccessible to video analysis, Goodwin's emphasis on observable embodied participation provides concrete behavioral indicators suitable for video analysis. We also chose Dillenbourg's collaborative learning framework (Dillenbourg, 1999) because it provides operationalizable criteria for distinguishing collaboration from cooperation (i.e., degree of symmetry in the interactions, common goals, and division of labor). This framework offers a systematic

approach to classifying different levels and types of collaborative engagement. It enables our study to move beyond binary collaboration detection to categorizing the quality and intensity of student interactions through observable behaviors. Together, these frameworks align with both the nonverbal nature of our data and the collaborative learning context of our analysis.

We adopted the batch-processing strategy demonstrated in Liu et al. (2024), as including all descriptions in a single prompt would exceed GPT-4o’s context window. We thus submitted 50 subsets of LLaVA-generated descriptions as a batch for independent open coding (500 transcriptions in total across 10 batches). Each batch ranged from 18485 to 19892 tokens, remaining within GPT-4o’s input limits. Processing each batch enabled the model to produce a distinct set of candidate codes, allowing us to detect recurring patterns and assess stability across iterations. Resulting codes were provided in Appendix 3.

4.4. CODEBOOK EVALUATION PROCESS

To evaluate and compare candidate codes generated across batches, we adapted the evaluation framework proposed by Chen et al. (2024) and extended it to include theoretical alignment. Our evaluation framework included the following dimensions:

Density: the depth of descriptive detail and conceptual richness, assessed by examining whether codes captured meaningful variation or relied on broad and vague categories.

Consistency Across Batches: the stability of codes across batches. This is informed by Chen et al.’s notions of *divergence* and *novelty*, which quantify how an individual coder’s contributions deviate from or extend a shared conceptual space. We adapted this to assess the recurrence of codes across codebooks generated from batches. Codes that reappeared with consistent labels or meanings were considered more robust, while codes that appeared only once were flagged for removal or revision.

Theoretical Alignment: the extent to which a codebook reflected constructs in established theoretical frameworks. We prioritized codes with greater alignment to established frameworks for retention and refinement.

Researchers reviewed each batch-level codebook using these criteria. The three evaluation dimensions provided a structured framework for qualitative assessment rather than numerical scoring. We documented the review process as visualized in Figure 5 through a revision log that tracked decisions and rationale at each iteration, ensuring systematic application of the qualitative criteria.

Figure 5: Visualization of the process for codebook refinement and consolidation.

Step 1: Within-Batch Code Consolidation. Researchers reviewed each individual batch to eliminate redundancy by merging codes with overlapping behavioral descriptions or definitions. We compared all codes within each batch for semantic similarity. Specifically, we examined code definitions, behavioral indicators, and theoretical grounding to identify potential overlaps. We merged codes when they described identical or highly similar behavioral patterns with no

meaningful distinction. For example, *Coordinated Co-Attention (CCA)* and *Reciprocal Collaboration (RC)* in Batch 4 were merged as both codes highlighted mutual coordination with joint focus and reciprocal behaviors. Similarly, *Parallel Individual Engagement* and *Focused Individual Work (Non-Collaborative)* in Batch 8 both described independent work without collaboration and were combined. This phase reduced the total code count from 69 to 63, ensuring each batch contributed distinct behavioral patterns while removing within-batch redundancy before cross-batch analysis.

Step 2: Cross-batch Code Comparison. We analyzed candidate codes from all batches to identify conceptually similar codes that appeared across multiple batches. We then grouped codes with similar descriptions and calculated the frequency as the number of batches in which it appeared. Through this analysis, we identified three conceptual patterns with 100% consistency (10/10 batches), meaning these behavioral patterns were universally recognized across all batches. These patterns included coordinated engagement (appearing as *Mutual Task Alignment* in Batch 1, *Focused Co-Engagement* in Batch 2, *Mutual Coordination* in Batch 3, etc.), parallel engagement (from *Parallel Individual Engagement* in Batch 1 & 10 to *Individual Parallelism* in Batch 9), and peripheral engagement (ranging from *Latent Collaboration Readiness* in Batch 1 to *Opportunistic Monitoring* in Batch 10). Asymmetric collaboration appeared in 9 out of 10 batches (90% frequency), while disengagement patterns appeared in 8 out of 10 batches (80% frequency). Overall, this systematic frequency analysis revealed five major conceptual groups with 80-100% cross-batch stability (see Appendix 3 for detailed code names in each batch).

Phase 3: Examination of Rare and Infrequent Codes. We further examined rare codes appearing once or twice for potential novelty. However, we typically removed or merged these codes if they lacked sufficient generalizability or method rigor. Several codes were removed due to limited generalizability. For instance, *Exploratory Triadic Exchange* in Batch 2 was specific to three-member groups and could not be applied to dyadic interactions that comprised 40% of our dataset. Other codes were removed due to methodological constraints. For example, *Silent Co-Attentive Work* in Batch 8 and *Task-Silent Synchrony* in Batch 9 required audio confirmation of silence, but LLaVA's inability to process audio data created potential for misclassification. More complex decisions involved codes describing temporal processes rather than momentary states, such as *Bridging Interaction*, *Transitional Alignment*, and *Task-Switching Synchrony*. These described dynamics over time rather than discrete behavioral states. After extensive discussion, we decided to code the predominant behavioral state within each segment rather than the transition process itself, as it is difficult to determine whether these transitions were behaviorally meaningful or simply artifacts of clip segmentation. During this process, we removed four codes and merged five codes into existing categories.

Step 4: Theoretical Alignment Evaluation. We qualitatively assessed each remaining code by mapping them to constructs from Goodwin's and Dillenbourg's frameworks. Specifically, we assessed how well each code related to Goodwin's concepts of embodied participation, stance-taking, and participation frameworks, as well as Dillenbourg's distinctions between collaboration and cooperation, symmetry/asymmetry, and shared cognitive responsibility. Codes with straightforward theoretical alignment were easily consolidated. For instance, asymmetric collaboration codes such as *Role-Asymmetric Coordination*, *Asymmetric Participation*, and *Asymmetric Facilitation* all mapped clearly to Goodwin's stance-taking and Dillenbourg's asymmetry in control and contribution, leading to their consolidation as Asymmetric Engagement. We retained codes without clear mapping to selected theoretical frameworks for further evaluation. Consistent patterns might represent novel collaborative states not captured in theoretical frameworks. This systematic process ultimately yielded four codes mapping clearly to

established theoretical constructs and one code without direct theoretical grounding but with sufficient empirical stability to warrant inclusion in the final codebook.

Step 5: Final Codebook Compilation. This process was repeated for all code categories. From this iterative refinement, we merged 11 codes due to semantic overlap and discarded eight codes for lack of consistency across batches, ambiguous definitions, or methodological constraints that prevented reliable coding. The remaining codes were consolidated into the final codes (see Table 4 for code definition and theoretical grounding).

4.5. PHASE 4: AI-ASSISTED CODING

Once the codebook was finalized through this iterative process, we applied the refined prompt to the full dataset of LLaVA-generated narrative descriptions. Researchers manually coded a subset of outputs (5% of the dataset) to verify alignment between model outputs and human interpretation. We also conducted a preliminary comparison among direct LLaVA video-based coding, GPT-4o transcript-based coding, and human coding. This comparison used the same finalized codebook and the same mutually exclusive coding structure across conditions, requiring the model to select one best-fitting code for each segment. The analysis showed stronger alignment between GPT coding and human coding than between direct video coding and human coding, suggesting that the transcript-based representation provided a more consistent basis for applying the finalized codebook across segments. The full results of this preliminary comparison are reported in Appendix 4. We then prompted GPT-4o to assign one of the behavior codes to each video segment. To guide consistent application, each prompt included: (a) study context description, (b) definitions of behavior categories, and (c) instructions for interpreting and applying each code.

5. RESULTS

This section presents findings from our systematic evaluation of the GAIVA framework across three key phases: behavioral transcription using MLLMs, theory-informed codebook development through human–AI collaboration, and automated coding with LLMs.

5.1. RQ1: EFFECTIVENESS OF MLLMS IN TRANSCRIBING NONVERBAL COLLABORATIVE BEHAVIORS

Following the procedure described in Phase 2, we evaluated 250 LLaVA transcriptions in total (five prompt strategies x 50 video segments; see Appendix 1 for examples of transcripts). Table 3 presents a summary of average scores and standard deviations across all prompt strategies. The evaluation revealed that the role-assignment achieved the most balanced performance in accuracy ($M = 3.24$, $SD = 1.72$), completeness ($M = 3.86$, $SD = 0.35$), and specificity ($M = 3.54$, $SD = 0.58$), compared to other strategies. Although the CoT-inspired prompt showed slightly higher accuracy ($M = 3.48$, $SD = 1.59$), it underperformed in completeness and specificity. The baseline zero-shot prompt showed the lowest overall performance: accuracy ($M = 2.74$, $SD = 1.75$), completeness ($M = 2.70$, $SD = 0.61$), and specificity ($M = 2.34$, $SD = 0.59$).

To examine whether these observed differences were statistically significant, we conducted Friedman tests for each dimension. The results indicated significant differences in scores across strategies for accuracy ($\chi^2 = 15.20$, $p = 0.004$), completeness ($\chi^2 = 86.52$, $p < 0.001$), and specificity ($\chi^2 = 74.49$, $p < 0.001$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Bonferroni correction revealed that the role-assignment prompt produced significantly

higher scores than most other strategies, particularly for the completeness and specificity dimensions.

Table 3: Average scores and standard deviations for each prompt strategy across all evaluated dimensions (scoring range 1-5 for accuracy, 1-4 for completeness and specificity).

Strategy	Accuracy	Completeness	Specificity
Baseline	2.74 (1.75)	2.70 (0.61)	2.34 (0.59)
Tone-adjusted	3.22 (1.66)	3.00 (0.49)	2.84 (0.55)
Role-assignment	3.24 (1.72)	3.86 (0.35)	3.54 (0.58)
Context	2.78 (1.58)	3.28 (0.57)	3.10 (0.61)
CoT-inspired	3.48 (1.59)	3.12 (0.59)	2.78 (0.65)

In addition to quantitative ratings, qualitative examination of model outputs revealed that the transcriptions preserved a high degree of detail and contextual richness. For example, the following excerpt illustrates how the model documented multiple aspects of students' gaze, posture, and engagement:

"Throughout the video, the students' gaze patterns and attention shifts indicate their level of engagement and collaboration. The student on the left occasionally looks up from his laptop to glance at the screen or at the other students, suggesting that he is paying attention to the discussion and is actively participating. The student in the middle maintains a steady focus on his laptop, indicating that he is deeply engaged in his work. The student on the right frequently looks up from his notebook to glance at the other students, suggesting that he is listening attentively and is interested in the discussion.

Body language also plays a role in signaling the students' level of focus and interaction. The student on the left has his elbows on the table and leans slightly forward, indicating that he is engaged and interested in the activity. The student in the middle sits back in his chair, suggesting a more relaxed posture, but still appears focused on his work. The student on the right sits upright and holds his notebook close, indicating that he is taking notes and is actively participating in the discussion."

This transcription highlights several capabilities that underpin MLLMs' utility. First, the model can distinguish individual behavioral differences with a high level of detail, differentiating between personal focus, peer monitoring, and active participation. These granular observations are essential for developing coding schemes that can differentiate between various collaborative engagement states (Jordan and Henderson, 1995; Barron, 2003; Cukurova et al., 2020). Importantly, because the transcripts are grounded in evidence such as "glance at peers" and "lean forward," researchers can more easily trace, examine, and validate interpretive claims to establish transparency and credibility for the analysis. Additionally, the model attends to multiple behavioral modalities, including gaze patterns, attention shifts, body posture, and tool engagement. It is capable of producing comprehensive behavioral accounts that capture both individual behaviors and group-level dynamics (Martinez-Maldonado et al., 2019; Cukurova et al., 2020). This level of completeness and specificity was maintained across video clips, demonstrating MLLMs' potential to scale analysis to large datasets.

5.2. RQ2: HUMAN–AI COLLABORATION IN DEVELOPING A THEORETICALLY GROUNDED CODEBOOK

The collaboration between researchers and GPT-4o yielded a final codebook composed of five behavior categories, as shown in Table 4. Four codes (Coordinated Collaboration, Asymmetric Collaboration, Parallel Engagement, and Disengagement) demonstrated clear alignment with established theoretical frameworks. One additional code (Peripheral Engagement) emerged with high empirical consistency across coding batches but lacked direct correspondence to the selected theoretical frameworks.

Table 4: Final codebook with theoretical grounding explained and IRR performance (κ) between Human/Human (H/H) and Human/GPT (H/G). *Note:* Disengagement was not observed in transcriptions selected for IRR check, so IRR is not reported for this code.

Code Name	Definition	Theoretical Grounding	H/H	H/G
Coordinated Collaboration	All group members exhibit synchronized embodied engagement in a shared task. Students align gaze, gesture, and posture to maintain joint attention, mutual understanding, and shared problem space.	Goodwin (2000, 2007): mutual orientation, shared semiotic fields; Dillenbourg (1999): symmetry, shared goals and low division of labor	0.83	0.91
Asymmetric Collaboration	One or more students take on directive or leadership roles, while others assume passive or responsive roles. Coordination is present, but participation is uneven or hierarchical.	Goodwin (2007): Stance and speaker roles; Dillenbourg (1999): Asymmetry in action and status	0.73	0.69
Peripheral Engagement	Students remain individually focused but display awareness of peers. This includes occasional glances, passive monitoring, or readiness to re-engage in group work.	/	0.78	0.63
Parallel Engagement	Students work independently on task-relevant activities, showing little to no interaction or mutual coordination.	Goodwin (2000, 2007): Lack of mutual orientation; Dillenbourg (1999): Division of labor, cooperation vs. collaboration	0.68	0.65
Disengagement	One or more students appear disengaged from the group or task.	Dillenbourg (1999)	/	/

5.3. RQ3: CODEBOOK RELIABILITY OF LLM-BASED AUTOMATED CODING

To evaluate the reliability of LLM-based coding, we compared GPT-4o's application of the final five-category codebook to human annotations on 50 randomly selected transcriptions. Table 4

summarizes the inter-rater reliability results. Notably, none of the segments were labeled as Disengagement, limiting the reliability analysis to the remaining four categories. Of the 50 segments, Peripheral Engagement was the most frequent code ($n = 18$), followed by Coordinated Collaboration ($n = 17$), Parallel Engagement ($n = 10$), and Asymmetric Collaboration ($n = 5$). Agreement between GPT-4o and the two human coders was generally moderate to substantial across codes. For Coordinated Collaboration, human–GPT agreement was highest ($\kappa = 0.91$), exceeding human–human agreement ($\kappa = 0.83$). For Asymmetric Collaboration, reliability was comparable, with human–GPT kappa at 0.69 and human–human at 0.73, indicating that the model could identify uneven participation with consistency similar to human raters. Agreement for Peripheral Engagement was moderate for human–GPT ($\kappa = 0.63$), while human–human agreement was higher ($\kappa = 0.78$), reflecting the greater interpretive ambiguity of this category. Parallel Engagement showed the lowest agreement overall, with $\kappa = 0.65$ for human–GPT and $\kappa = 0.68$ for human–human. Overall, the results suggest that GPT-4o applied the codebook reliably across most categories, particularly for Coordinated Collaboration, where visual cues were more salient.

6. DISCUSSION

We introduce GAIVA, a modular human–AI collaboration framework designed to address a persistent tension in educational video research: how to scale qualitative analysis without sacrificing interpretive depth or theoretical rigor (Snell, 2011; Blikstad-Balas, 2017). As illustrated in our results, this pipeline offers a robust foundation for analyzing embodied participation and collaborative dynamics at scale. It enables the automated transcription of nonverbal behaviors, the co-construction of a theoretically grounded codebook, and automated coding. To answer our overarching research question (To what extent can current GenAI models support scalable, consistent, and theoretically grounded qualitative video analysis?), we structured our study around three research sub-questions. In the sections that follow, we synthesize our findings across these dimensions, outline practical strategies for implementing GAIVA, and discuss the use cases and limitations that determine where GAIVA is most effective.

We evaluated **scalability** in RQ1, which examined the efficiency and quality of MLLM-generated transcriptions of nonverbal collaborative behaviors. Qualitative video analysis is time-intensive and prone to interpretive variation and coder fatigue (Snell, 2011; Lemke, 2014). Our results indicate that MLLMs can improve scalability by automating the transcription process, enabling researchers to process larger volumes of video data more efficiently without compromising description quality. Human ratings confirmed strong agreement between model-generated outputs and researcher interpretations. For example, across the full set of strategies tested, model outputs achieved moderate to high scores on accuracy and completeness (e.g., *role assignment*: $M = 3.24$ for accuracy; $M = 3.86$ for completeness). An accuracy score at this level (3.24 out of 5) means that all relevant interaction behaviors were described correctly, with inaccuracies confined primarily to irrelevant details (e.g., background objects) and remaining below the 50% threshold as defined in our scoring criteria. Likewise, the high mean completeness score (3.86 out of 4) indicates that the transcriptions consistently captured all required behavioral dimensions and often included additional relevant cues. Qualitative review further confirmed that the transcriptions captured nuanced behavioral differences and multiple modalities of interactions. This combination of breadth and detail enables researchers to document complex collaborative processes at scale while maintaining analytical depth. Together, these results suggest that the transcription layer provided a sufficient descriptive foundation for the

subsequent coding in this study. Although the transcriptions were not error-free, the remaining inaccuracies were irrelevant to the analytic goal of interpreting students' collaborative interaction patterns and therefore did not affect the coding outcomes.

However, while automation improved overall efficiency and scalability, it still faced the challenge of interpretive ambiguity. The model occasionally produced plausible but unsupported statements about students' intentions or engagement levels—for example, inferring that a student was engaged or off-task without clear behavioral evidence. This is similar to overinterpretation issues noted in other work where MLLMs tend to generate plausible-sounding outputs based on learned patterns, rather than visually grounded cues (Zhou et al., 2025). Although MLLMs can transcribe surface-level behaviors, they should not be treated as independent interpreters of students' cognitive or affective states. This highlights the importance of maintaining a human-in-the-loop process. MLLMs advance the scalability of qualitative video analysis by automating the transcription and behavioral documentation stages. However, they do not replace the need for researchers to validate interpretations, apply theoretical lenses, and make context-sensitive judgments about meaning and intentions.

Consistency in traditional video analysis is often compromised by the lack of standardized protocols for segmentation and coding. Without clear and repeatable decision rules, researchers may selectively magnify certain video segments or apply codes inconsistently, limiting the replicability and generalizability of findings across researchers or studies (Hammersley, 2010; Blikstad-Balas, 2017). GAIVA addresses this limitation through a structured pipeline that enforces consistency across all stages of the analysis. By applying uniform decision rules and deterministic settings, such as zero-temperature outputs during code generation, GAIVA minimizes variability introduced by subjective judgment, coder fatigue, or interpretive drift over time. This level of reproducibility and transparency is difficult to achieve through fully manual approaches. Similar codes emerged across independently processed data batches, suggesting that LLMs can support the discovery of consistent coding patterns by reducing some variability associated with individual coder fatigue or subtle shifts in interpretation over time. This consistency is especially valuable in large-scale studies, where cross-group and cross-researcher comparability is critical for ensuring validity (Hammersley, 2010). It is also important to note that individual perspectives and theoretical lenses still shape the analytic process as researchers still play a critical role in interpreting, aligning, and consolidating model-generated code.

At the same time, this procedural consistency introduces its own challenges. Because LLMs rely on pre-trained heuristics and linguistic structures drawn from large, generic datasets, there is a risk that culturally specific or contextually nuanced behaviors will be systematically underrepresented or mischaracterized (Blodgett et al., 2020; Bender et al., 2021). For instance, in several instances, the model tended to default to generic descriptors of “paying attention” or “being engaged” without distinguishing finer-grained differences in interactional dynamics that may be analytically significant in certain educational contexts. This limitation reflects a tension between consistency and contextual sensitivity: while LLMs improve reproducibility and mitigate some forms of inconsistency, they can also flatten variability and generate interpretations that align with their training data. As a result, although GAIVA supports consistent and replicable coding, there exists the need for iterative human validation to ensure that analytic stability does not come at the cost of contextual relevance and analytical depth.

In RQ3, we examined **theoretical alignment** by evaluating how well GAIVA's outputs mapped onto established frameworks of embodied participation, mutual attention, and coordination (Dillenbourg, 1999; Goodwin, 2000, 2007). Historically, researcher-led coding has been valued for preserving coherence with established theories but critiqued for limiting openness to emergent or context-specific constructs (Erickson, 2006; Hammersley, 2010). Our findings

highlight that GAIVA can support both aims, maintaining alignment with existing frameworks while creating space for inductive discovery. On one hand, the pipeline reliably reproduced core theoretical categories, demonstrating that AI-facilitated analysis can achieve alignment with established theoretical frameworks. At the same time, GAIVA identified recurring patterns (i.e., *Peripheral Engagement*) that were not pre-specified but emerged consistently across multiple coding batches generated interdependently by the model. This construct was characterized by individual focus coupled with peer awareness and readiness for engagement. While this construct had no direct theoretical precedent in our selected frameworks, conceptually similar patterns emerged across all ten independently generated codebooks, suggesting a high degree of empirical recurrence. Goodwin's framework focuses on embodied participation through mutual orientation and shared attention, emphasizing collaborative states where participants actively coordinate their actions. Dillenbourg's framework distinguishes between cooperation (division of labor where individuals work independently toward shared goals) and collaboration. However, *Peripheral Engagement* occupies a distinct middle ground: students maintain individual focus while demonstrating awareness of peers and readiness to transition into collaborative interaction when needed.

This dual capability—maintaining alignment with established categories and surfacing new ones—illustrates the potential of structured human-in-the loop collaboration to contribute not only to theoretical alignment but also to research-guided theory building. Notably, such inductive discoveries can be challenging in traditional qualitative workflows when factors such as cognitive load, limited time, and the inherent complexity of social interactions can make it difficult to consistently notice and document subtle or ambiguous behaviors across large datasets (Heath et al., 2010; Snell, 2011). GAIVA helps address these limitations through its modular and scalable design, which separates transcription, interpretation, codebook generation, and coding into discrete phases. First, the MLLM generates consistent behavioral descriptions across large video corpora. The LLM then processes these descriptions to create codebooks across multiple batches, enabling researchers to examine whether the same constructs emerge independently. Traditional small-scale qualitative approaches rarely afford this level of systematic comparison, making it difficult to assess whether emergent codes are stable, recurrent, or contextually dependent over time (Derry et al., 2010).

Furthermore, GAIVA preserves a transparent link between descriptive transcripts and resulting codes. This allows researchers to trace each construct back to its underlying behavioral evidence. This traceability supports more rigorous review, validation, and refinement of emergent categories, addressing common challenges in qualitative research where the rationale behind code development is often implicit or undocumented (Erickson, 2006; Derry et al., 2010; Jewitt, 2012). At each step, GAIVA logs both model outputs and researchers' decisions and documents how interpretations evolve and how theoretical or empirical criteria are applied. This design promotes analytical transparency and replication, while ensuring that the role of researcher judgment remains visible throughout the workflow.

Taken together, these capabilities suggest that GAIVA not only supports theoretical alignment with existing frameworks but also facilitates the empirical discovery and iterative validation of new constructs. However, this also raises important questions about validation and interpretive responsibility. When new categories are surfaced through model-driven processes rather than human-led analysis, researchers must determine how to evaluate their credibility, clarify their relationship to existing frameworks, and assess whether they reflect meaningful aspects of collaboration or artifacts of the model's training data. In this context, researcher expertise remains essential for distinguishing analytical value from statistical coincidence.

6.1. IMPLEMENTATION INSIGHTS AND PRACTICAL GUIDANCE

6.1.1. Where Human Insights Remain Important

From the process of developing, validating, and refining GAIVA, several takeaways emerged. One of the central challenges in using generative AI for qualitative analysis is ensuring that the analytic process remains transparent, interpretable, and grounded in evidence. We identified three areas where human oversight plays a critical role in transforming model outputs into research-valid insights: transcription assessment, construct consistency validation, and theoretical interpretation.

First, high-quality transcription is foundational as it directly impacts any downstream analytical tasks (Derry et al., 2010; Goldman et al., 2014). While MLLMs like LLaVA can process visual input and produce descriptions at scale, we discovered that the research utility of these outputs depends not only on factual accuracy but also on their completeness (i.e., how comprehensively they capture relevant behaviors) and specificity (i.e., whether they provide concrete observable details). These criteria became essential in assessing whether the outputs were adequate for downstream interpretation (Bezemer and Mavers, 2011; Snell, 2011). Importantly, our case study revealed that transcription quality varies significantly depending on prompt design and context, underscoring the need for researchers to systematically check and refine outputs before any downstream coding.

Second, validating the consistency of emergent constructs requires human evaluation. Rather than relying on a single codebook, researchers must compare outputs across batches and determine which constructs recur consistently (e.g., Peripheral Engagement) and which are more likely to be prompt-dependent or context-specific. Traditional small-scale qualitative workflows often lack the capacity to conduct this level of systematic cross-batch comparison, making it challenging to evaluate the stability and generalizability of emerging codes (Hammersley, 2010; Blikstad-Balas, 2017). GAIVA supports this need by embedding consistency checks into the analysis process and treating recurrence across batches as an indicator of empirical robustness.

Third, we discovered that integrating theoretical frameworks into AI-assisted coding requires active, ongoing validation rather than one-time alignment checking. Even when the model proposes labels or mappings, researchers must assess whether these outputs meaningfully align with theoretical constructs, consolidate codebooks, and document interpretive decisions. Without this critical engagement, theoretical alignment risks becoming superficial and/or inconsistent.

These insights demonstrate that successful AI-assisted qualitative analysis requires analytical workflows that preserve interpretive traceability, encourage multi-pass validation, and integrate human reasoning throughout. While GAIVA provides scalability, human insight remains essential to ensure interpretive rigor and theoretical coherence.

6.1.2. New Research Possibilities and Ideal Use Cases

GenAI models open research possibilities that have long been constrained by the labor-intensive nature of manual video analysis. Most video studies remain confined to micro-level snapshots, often focusing on short excerpts rather than entire lessons or extended sequences (Lemke, 2014; Blikstad-Balas, 2017). While large-scale coding initiatives like PISA+ (Klette, 2009) have demonstrated the value of combining standardized coding with detailed analysis, they also highlight the considerable resources such work demands. The need for repeated viewing, transcription, and annotation of complex classroom interactions has historically made it difficult to scale qualitative video research beyond small samples (Heath et al., 2010; Jewitt, 2012). This

reliance on limited data increases the risk of sampling bias, as brief episodes are sometimes treated as representative of broader practices (Miller and Zhou, 2014). In this context, MLLMs offer promising tools for overcoming long-standing constraints on scale. By automating transcription and generating structured behavioral descriptions across large datasets, these models help researchers trace emergent patterns without losing interpretive depth. GAIVA builds on these advances by making large-scale video analysis more practical and accessible. Researchers can now examine hundreds of hours of footage that would otherwise require a huge amount of manual effort (Markle et al., 2011). This scalability enables longitudinal studies that track learning behaviors across semesters or school years, as well as comparative investigations of diverse groups, contexts, and instructional approaches. With lower barriers to processing extensive video corpora, GAIVA makes it possible to identify trends that emerge only at scale and to validate findings across varied educational settings.

In addition to scalability, a particular strength of GAIVA lies in its capacity to support multimodal analysis of nonverbal and embodied interactions. The framework can systematically document patterns such as gaze shifts, gesture coordination, spatial positioning, and tool use—behaviors that are often theoretically central to collaboration but frequently under-analyzed due to the complexity of transcription and coding (Martinez-Maldonado et al., 2019; Cukurova et al., 2020). This capability enables researchers to examine embodied dimensions of learning in much greater detail, including how physical proximity relates to participation or how synchronized gestures signal shared understanding and joint attention. By making these behaviors more accessible for large-scale analysis, GAIVA helps examine the physical and spatial aspects of collaborative learning.

However, GAIVA is not a one-size-fits-all solution. Its effectiveness depends on the alignment between methodological choices and research context. GAIVA demonstrates greatest effectiveness when researchers have clear, well-defined research goals rather than open-ended exploration of video corpora. Many methodological decisions—from prompt selection to video preprocessing parameters to theoretical frameworks guiding codebook development—require substantial understanding of both the video content and research purpose. The framework performs optimally for goal-oriented inquiries where researchers can specify target behaviors, select appropriate theoretical frameworks, and design validation protocols aligned with their analytical objectives.

GAIVA's technical capabilities also align best with research questions that focus on nonverbal and visually observable behaviors. Because the framework relies on vision-based transcription without integrated audio processing, it is especially effective for documenting embodied aspects of collaboration, including gaze coordination, spatial positioning, and material engagement. Studies examining verbal discourse, prosodic cues, or subtle audio-dependent interactions may require complementary transcription tools or additional workflows to capture these dimensions comprehensively.

Finally, dataset size is a critical consideration when determining whether GAIVA is appropriate. Although the framework significantly reduces per-segment analysis time, it requires considerable upfront investment in prompt engineering, codebook development, and validation to ensure interpretive rigor. For smaller datasets, traditional manual approaches may remain more flexible and efficient, particularly when researchers want full control over interpretive decisions. In contrast, for projects involving hundreds of hours of video, GAIVA's scalability becomes increasingly compelling, enabling consistent coding across large collections that would otherwise be infeasible to analyze in depth.

6.2. LIMITATIONS

While GAIVA demonstrates promising potential for scaling qualitative video analysis, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the framework operates exclusively on vision-based data, without access to audio streams. As a result, it cannot capture verbal cues such as verbal discourse and audio-dependent collaborative behaviors such as speech patterns, vocal turn-taking, or prosodic indicators of engagement. Future research should explore multimodal integration, particularly through the incorporation of audio analysis into the MLLM transcription layer. This could enable researchers to study how verbal and nonverbal modalities intertwine in collaborative learning.

Second, the approach depends heavily on video quality and visibility requirements. Students must be clearly and consistently captured by cameras for MLLMs to generate meaningful behavioral transcriptions. Situations involving occlusion, overlapping bodies, or dynamic camera movement may reduce the effectiveness of transcription and coding. These technical requirements limit the framework's applicability in less controlled or more crowded classroom environments. Future development could involve training or fine-tuning MLLMs on more diverse and noisy classroom video data to increase their robustness or pairing them with person-tracking algorithms to maintain continuity across occluded scenes. Improvements in camera placement protocols or multimodal sensor fusion could also expand GAIVA's practical deployment in live classrooms.

Third, the use of fixed-length segmentation (e.g., 10-second clips) introduces artificial boundaries that may not align with the natural flow of interaction. While this approach supports standardization, it can fragment coherent behavioral sequences or create artificial transitions that do not reflect genuine collaborative patterns. Meaningful collaborative interactions often unfold across varying timeframes—from brief gesture exchanges to extended problem-solving episodes—that may be disrupted by arbitrary temporal divisions. Future work should explore event-based segmentation approaches that identify natural behavioral boundaries, such as task transitions or interaction episode markers (e.g., tool use, gaze change), or even physiological signals.

The fourth limitation concerns the context-window size of GPT-4o, which directly shaped the design of Phase 3. Because the model could not process an unlimited amount of text at once, the full set of LLaVA-generated transcriptions had to be divided into smaller batches. While this batching process ensured feasibility, it also reduced the model's exposure to less frequent behavioral patterns that could inform the breadth of the resulting codebook. Future work may explore long-context LLMs or retrieval-augmented summarization strategies that allow models to process larger amounts of video transcriptions in a single call.

Fifth, the current evaluation does not provide a claim-level error analysis or determine how specific transcription errors may propagate into downstream coding outcomes. The transcription evaluation was designed to compare prompt strategies and assess transcript-level adequacy for subsequent coding, rather than to quantify the prevalence of every specific behavioral error. Future work should conduct more fine-grained analyses of transcript claims and examine how errors at the transcription stage affect subsequent code application.

Finally, although GAIVA reduces manual labor, it does not eliminate subjective or theory-driven decisions that shape the scope and interpretation of findings. Choices such as which behaviors to track, which theoretical framework to apply, or how to construct effective prompts all reflect researchers' theoretical preferences and prior knowledge. These decisions influence not only what the model attends to, but also what it misses. Similarly, the behavioral constructs that models can reliably detect are still limited by current MLLM and LLM capabilities. As

such, the framework's analytical reach is bounded both by technical constraints and theoretical framing. Addressing this will require greater transparency in reporting prompt design and codebook development, as well as tools for auditing model outputs and exposing analytic blind spots. In sum, while GAIVA represents an important step toward scalable and rigorous qualitative video analysis, its continued evolution will depend on advancing multimodal capabilities, refining temporal granularity, improving robustness to real-world conditions, and developing community standards for prompt and theory transparency.

7. CONCLUSION

This study introduced GAIVA, a framework that combines generative AI with human expertise to support qualitative video analysis at scale. By integrating MLLMs for behavioral transcription and LLMs for theory-informed coding, GAIVA addresses key challenges in traditional video analysis—especially the time demands, coding consistency, and need for theoretical grounding. Our results show that GAIVA can produce detailed and accurate descriptions of student behavior, support the development of stable and theoretically aligned codebooks, and apply those codes reliably across larger datasets. The framework also identified a recurring behavioral pattern—*Peripheral Engagement*—that was not defined in our initial theoretical models but appeared consistently across multiple coding rounds. This suggests that GAIVA can support both theory-driven and data-driven approaches to understanding collaborative learning. In addition to improving efficiency and consistency, GAIVA promotes transparency by structuring the analysis into clear phases where researcher oversight remains central. This helps ensure that AI-generated outputs stay connected to the research goals, theoretical frameworks, and context of the study. At the same time, GAIVA has limitations. It currently focuses on visual behaviors and does not include audio, which may limit its ability to capture certain kinds of interaction. It also relies on fixed-length video segments, which may cut across natural boundaries in student activity. Future work should explore how to include audio and how to segment videos based on meaningful events rather than time intervals. Overall, GAIVA offers a practical and flexible approach for researchers who want to scale qualitative video analysis without losing interpretive depth. It is especially useful for studies focused on collaboration, embodiment, and classroom interaction—areas where rich multimodal data are essential but difficult to analyze manually at scale.

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DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI SOFTWARE TOOLS IN THE WRITING PROCESS

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APPENDIX 1: LLaVA GENERATED TRANSCRIPTS

This appendix provides several randomly selected examples of the video transcriptions produced by LLaVA-Video-72B-Qwen2 for 10-second clips. These examples illustrate the typical level of verbosity, the granularity of nonverbal behavioral cues captured (e.g., gaze, posture, gesture), and the descriptive structure of the outputs prior to codebook development.

Example 1

The video depicts a classroom setting where two students are seated at a table, engaged in an activity that appears to be a discussion or collaborative work. The student on the left is wearing a white hoodie and is seen pointing at a piece of paper, which suggests he is explaining or discussing something with his peer. His gaze is directed towards the paper, indicating focus and engagement in the task.

The student on the right, dressed in a black shirt, is looking down at the paper, following the direction of the other student's finger. This behavior indicates active listening and attention to the content being discussed. The student's body language, with shoulders relaxed and leaning slightly forward, suggests openness and interest in the interaction.

Both students have papers and pens in front of them, and there are additional items on the table such as a phone and a notebook, which may be used for reference or note-taking. The presence of these materials implies that the students are prepared and involved in a structured educational activity.

The background shows a window with blinds partially drawn, allowing natural light into the room, and a chair is visible to the side, suggesting a typical classroom environment. The overall atmosphere appears calm and conducive to learning.

The interactions between the students, characterized by direct gaze, gesturing, and attentive postures, reflect a collaborative dynamic. The student in the white hoodie takes on a more active role in guiding the discussion, while the student in the black shirt participates by focusing on the material and responding to cues from his peer. These behaviors signal a level of comfort and familiarity with each other, indicative of a positive learning environment.

Example 2

The video shows a group of students sitting around a table in what appears to be a classroom or study setting. The students are engaged in a discussion or collaborative activity, as indicated by their body language and gaze patterns.

One student, wearing a brown jacket with a fur collar, is seen writing on a piece of paper. This student's posture is slightly leaned forward, indicating focus and engagement in the task at hand. The student's gaze is directed downwards towards the paper, and their hand movements suggest they are actively writing.

Another student, wearing a white shirt, is seen holding a piece of paper and looking at it intently. This student's gaze pattern is fixed on the paper, and their body language suggests concentration and attention to the content of the paper. The student's hand movements are minimal, indicating that they are primarily focused on reading or reviewing the information on the paper.

A third student, wearing a brown shirt, is seen looking at the student in the white shirt. This student's gaze pattern is directed towards the other student, and their body language suggests they are engaged in the discussion or activity. The student's hand movements are also minimal, indicating that they are primarily focused on listening or observing the other student.

Overall, the students' body language and gaze patterns suggest a level of focus and engagement in the collaborative activity. The student in the brown jacket appears to be actively participating in the task, while the student in the white shirt is concentrating on reviewing information. The student in the brown shirt is also engaged, as indicated by their gaze pattern directed towards the other student. These behaviors reflect a collaborative learning environment where students are working together to achieve a common goal.

Example 3

The video depicts a classroom setting where students are engaged in collaborative work. The students are seated at tables, with laptops and papers spread out in front of them. The room is equipped with large screens displaying information relevant to their task.

Observing the interactions between students, we can see that they exhibit a range of non-verbal behavioral cues that indicate their level of engagement and collaboration. For instance, one student, wearing a striped sweater, is seen leaning forward and directing her gaze towards her laptop screen, suggesting she is deeply focused on her work. Her body language, with shoulders squared and hands actively typing, signals a high level of concentration and involvement.

Adjacent to her, another student in a brown hoodie is also engrossed in his laptop, but occasionally looks up and turns his head towards the student in the striped sweater. This gaze pattern suggests that he is seeking input or clarification from his peer, indicating a collaborative dynamic. His attention shifts between his own screen and his partner, reflecting a balance between independent work and group interaction.

Further observation reveals that the student in the striped sweater reciprocates this gaze pattern by periodically looking up and engaging with the student in the brown hoodie. This mutual eye contact and orientation towards each other reinforce the notion of a collaborative effort, where both students are actively participating in a shared learning process.

In the background, other students are also engaged in similar activities, with some looking at their screens intently, while others are discussing amongst themselves. The overall atmosphere appears to be one of focused productivity, with students immersed in their tasks and interacting with their peers as needed.

The observable behaviors in this classroom setting, such as gaze patterns, attention shifts, and body language, provide valuable insights into the students' level of focus and interaction. These non-verbal cues are essential for understanding group dynamics and the effectiveness of collaborative learning environments.

APPENDIX 2: PROMPT FOR CODEBOOK GENERATION

Assume the role of an experienced researcher specialized in qualitative analysis, multimodal video analysis, and collaborative learning. Your task is to examine video transcripts detailing students' non-verbal interactions during a collaborative science activity. In these sessions, college students worked in groups of two or three using a web-based simulation to explore planetary systems and investigate Kepler's laws.

Create a codebook that synthesizes non-verbal behaviors (such as gaze, gestures, and attention) into high-level patterns summarizing the collaboration status. Each pattern should clearly illustrate how students engage with the task, interact with each other, and utilize shared resources. Ensure each code is mutually exclusive and applies to the entire transcript. Explicitly ground your analysis in the theoretical frameworks provided by:

- Goodwin, C. (2000). *Action and embodiment within situated human interaction*. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 32(10), 1489-1522.
- Goodwin, C. (2007). Participation, stance and affect in the organization of activities. *Discourse & society*, 18(1), 53-73.
- Dillenbourg, P. (1999). *What do you mean by collaborative learning?*. In *Collaborative-learning: Cognitive and Computational Approaches* (pp. 1-19). Elsevier.

Your codebook should include:

- **Concise labels** for each interactional pattern.
- **Brief definitions** clearly articulating each label.
- **Typical examples** illustrating representative behaviors.

APPENDIX 3: BATCH-LEVEL CODEBOOK

Table 2: Codebook from batch 1.

Label	Definition	Typical Non-Verbal Indicators
Mutual Task Alignment	All group members exhibit coordinated, mutual engagement in a shared task using gaze, gesture, and posture to establish joint attention.	Synchronized gaze on shared screen or paper; pointing or gesturing to shared materials; open body posture oriented toward group; reciprocal nods or affirming gestures.
Distributed but Aligned Focus	Group members are focused on different parts of the task (e.g., typing, writing, referencing materials), yet maintain visual or bodily awareness of each other.	Alternating gaze between peers and individual resources; brief eye contact; posture slightly oriented toward peers.
Role-Asymmetric Coordination	One student takes a more directive role (e.g., leading, explaining), while others adopt a responsive or listening role, creating a visible participation framework.	One student gesturing, pointing, or explaining; others nodding, writing, following with gaze; physical orientation toward speaker.
Parallel Individual Engagement	Students are individually focused with minimal signs of collaboration, but exhibit no signs of disengagement.	Sustained gaze on own laptop or paper; upright posture; minimal eye contact with peers.
Latent Collaboration Readiness	Students appear individually engaged, but intermittent gaze shifts or gestures suggest potential readiness to interact.	Quick glances toward peers; partial orientation toward group; hand resting mid-gesture; momentary pauses in work.
Disjointed Participation	Some group members are engaged while others are disengaged or distracted, leading to a fractured interactional frame.	One student using a phone or distracted; others show task focus and attempt to engage; lack of mutual gaze.

Label	Definition	Typical Non-Verbal Indicators
Co-Present but Disengaged	Students are physically co-located but lack signs of task engagement or interaction; attention is misaligned and fragmented.	Gaze fixed on personal device (e.g., phone); slouched posture; no gaze exchanges; no task-related gestures.

Table 2: Codebook from batch 2.

Code Label	Definition	Representative Behaviors
Focused Co-Engagement	All group members are simultaneously engaged in task-oriented activity, with aligned attention and shared focus on the same resource or idea.	- Synchronized gaze toward a shared screen or one student's laptop- Frequent eye contact and gestural references (e.g., pointing, nodding)- Leaning in or physically orienting bodies toward the same space- Simultaneous typing/writing with periodic pauses for mutual monitoring- Shared verbal or non-verbal affirmations (nodding, mirroring)
Parallel Individual Work	Students work in parallel on related subtasks with minimal interaction but show occasional non-verbal signs of mutual awareness.	- Sustained gaze on individual screens or notebooks- Occasional sideways glances toward peers or shared resources- Limited but strategic gestures (e.g., showing a screen or briefly pointing)- Slight shifts in posture suggesting attentiveness to peer activity without interruption- Moments of silence or only brief, pragmatic exchanges
Responsive Dyadic Coordination	Two students engage in a focused exchange, often with one taking a temporary expert/leader role while the other follows or responds.	- Alternating gaze between peer and shared object- Gestures such as pointing or turning the screen to a peer- Head nods, reciprocal eye contact, and verbal confirmations- One student explaining, the other listening/writing or responding with gestures- Clear turn-taking and attentive body posture toward each other
Fragmented Multitasking	Group members divide attention between individual and group activities, leading to uneven coordination and inconsistent interaction.	- One or more students alternating gaze between phone, laptop, and peer- Shifts in posture away from group (e.g., leaning back, crossed arms)- Unreciprocated glances or ignored gestures- One student appears highly engaged while others appear distracted- Minimal synchrony in task progression or timing
Distributed Leadership	Multiple students take initiative at different moments, guiding the task through gestures, gaze, or bodily orientation while others alternate between leading and following.	- Sequential pointing, gesturing, or screen sharing among students- Shifts in gaze and posture toward the current leader- Head tilts, nods, or forward leans indicating turn-taking in leadership- Rotating focus as peers respond to one another's initiatives- Cross-referencing

Code Label	Definition	Representative Behaviors
		between laptops or notes with rotating focal actors
Low Engagement / Peripheral Participation	One or more group members remain passive or disengaged while others are active. Their non-verbal behaviors show limited interaction or responsiveness.	- Prolonged gaze at phone or off-task materials- Slouched posture, head resting on hand, or leaning away- Lack of gaze reciprocation or gesture following- Minimal orientation toward group conversation or shared tools- Passive behaviors like silent nodding without contribution or movement
Exploratory Triadic Exchange	All three group members interact fluidly, with dynamic shifts in attention, mutual referencing, and co-construction of ideas.	- Triangular gaze exchange (A looks at B, then C; B gestures to A, etc.)- Overlapping talk supported by reinforcing gestures- Multimodal referencing (e.g., one writes while others talk and gesture)- Coordinated turns in speaking, writing, and referencing shared tools- Embodied displays of agreement (e.g., simultaneous leaning forward, shared laughter, mutual gestures toward a screen)

Table 3: Codebook from batch 3.

Code Label	Definition	Typical Behaviors	Theoretical Grounding
Mutual Coordination	All group members are actively engaged with each other and the shared task, co-constructing knowledge through sustained gaze, gestures, and posture alignment.	Gaze switching between peers and shared screens; leaning in; pointing; nodding; synchronized task engagement.	Goodwin (2007): co-participation; Dillenbourg (1999): high symmetry of action and knowledge.
Parallel Engagement	Students are individually focused on their own sub-tasks, but oriented toward a common group goal; minimal but meaningful coordination.	Gaze focused on laptops/papers; occasional mutual glances; silent information sharing; working side-by-side.	Goodwin (2000): shared space; Dillenbourg: medium symmetry, distributed tasks.
Asymmetric Collaboration	One or two students take a dominant role in the task (e.g., explaining, demonstrating), while others observe or minimally respond.	One student gesturing, pointing, or leading discussion; others nod, glance, or briefly respond with minimal gestures.	Goodwin (2007): stance-taking; Dillenbourg: asymmetry in control and contribution.

Code Label	Definition	Typical Behaviors	Theoretical Grounding
Coordinated Silence	All group members are focused silently on the shared materials or task, suggesting implicit synchronization and mutual attentiveness.	No talking; coordinated gaze on screens or papers; synchronized writing or typing; aligned body postures.	Goodwin (2000): embodied alignment; Dillenbourg: task interdependence with low verbal exchange.
Peripheral Monitoring	One or more students are actively working, while another is observing quietly or waiting to contribute. Engagement is uneven but still potentially collaborative.	One student watching others work, occasionally shifting gaze or posture; leaning back; minimal hand gestures.	Goodwin (2007): layered participation; Dillenbourg: asymmetry in engagement.
Isolated Focus	Students are physically co-present but cognitively and interactionally disengaged from each other, with no observable collaborative interaction.	Students work in silence without gaze shifts; closed posture; fixed gaze on individual materials; no gesturing.	Goodwin (2000): lack of interactional reciprocity; Dillenbourg: no collaboration.

Table 4: Codebook from batch 4.

Code Label	Definition	Typical Indicators & Examples
Parallel Individual Engagement (PIE)	Students are co-located but working independently, with minimal observable coordination or mutual orientation.	- Sustained gaze on personal devices or papers- No gestures or gaze toward peers- No verbal/non-verbal interaction Ex: All students quietly focused on laptops with no interaction (26:00–26:10)
Distributed Individual Focus with Peripheral Awareness (DIF-PA)	Students focus on individual tasks while maintaining low-level awareness of peers or group activity.	- Alternating gaze between task and peers/screens- Open body posture- Brief glances without follow-up Ex: Students glancing at shared screen while working individually (19:10–19:20)
Coordinated Co-Attention (CCA)	Students show synchronized orientation toward shared resources or content.	- Shared gaze on laptop, paper, or screen- Pointing or gesturing at common objects- Leaning in toward same focal point Ex: Two students pointing and looking at same screen (33:10–33:20)
Asymmetric Collaboration (AC)	One student leads or explains while others primarily listen or follow.	- One student gesturing, explaining, or pointing- Others nodding, writing,

Code Label	Definition	Typical Indicators & Examples
		or listening- Gaze primarily toward leading student Ex: One student explains while peer nods or listens (14:40–14:50)
Reciprocal Collaboration (RC)	Students engage in turn-taking, co-regulated interaction with mutual attention.	- Back-and-forth gestures, gaze shifts, shared turns- Responsive postures and gaze- Engagement with shared artifact and each other Ex: Students co-constructing explanation while pointing, nodding (15:20–15:30)
Fragmented Engagement (FE)	Collaboration is weak or interrupted due to distraction, disinterest, or misalignment.	- Gaze at phone or away from task- Lack of mutual orientation- Closed body posture, no engagement gestures Ex: One student on phone while others try to work (25:20–25:30)

Table 5: Codebook from batch 5.

Code Label	Definition	Typical Behaviors	Theoretical Anchors
Coordinated Mutual Engagement (CME)	All group members are actively co-oriented toward the task, using gaze, gestures, and posture to maintain mutual understanding and shared focus.	Mutual gaze, synchronized attention shifts to shared resources, pointing or gesturing while speaking, responsive nodding, and leaning in toward group members.	Goodwin (2000, 2007); Dillenbourg (1999) – Co-construction through embodied coordination.
Parallel Individual Engagement (PIE)	Students work on the same task in physical proximity but without interacting or coordinating with each other.	Sustained focus on individual laptops or papers, minimal eye contact, independent posture, absence of turn-taking or shared references.	Dillenbourg (1999); Goodwin (2007) – Co-location without co-participation.
Asymmetric Participation (ASP)	One student leads or dominates the activity, while others take on a passive, receptive, or peripheral role.	One person gesturing or speaking while others remain still, listeners rarely reciprocating gaze, minimal verbal/gestural response from others, uneven body orientation.	Goodwin (2007); Dillenbourg (1999) – Unequal participation and limited mutual regulation.
Coordinated Turn-Taking (CTT)	Students manage contributions sequentially and respectfully, with	Alternating speech or writing roles, gaze shift before speaking, pauses allowing peer input, collaborative	Goodwin (2000); Dillenbourg (1999) – Embodied regulation

Code Label	Definition	Typical Behaviors	Theoretical Anchors
	attention to timing, clarity, and group rhythm.	referencing of shared artifacts (e.g., pointing and passing items).	of turn-taking and task distribution.
Monitoring-with-Readiness (MWR)	Students work individually but remain peripherally aware of peers, ready to shift into collaboration as needed.	Side-glances, posture angled toward group, pausing own task to attend to peer actions, momentary eye contact, hand hover or readiness cues (e.g., reaching for shared device).	Goodwin (2007); Dillenbourg (1999) – Transitional participation and contingent collaboration.
Disengaged Presence (DP)	One or more students are physically present but show signs of task withdrawal, distraction, or non-participation.	Staring at phone, slouched posture, looking away from task or peers, arms crossed or head down, unresponsiveness to group cues.	Goodwin (2007); Dillenbourg (1999) – Peripheral or absent participation in collaborative settings.
Bridging Interaction (BI)	A student mediates between individual and group work, prompting collaboration or supporting group cohesion.	Alternating gaze between peers and task, physically orienting shared materials, initiating peer engagement through gestures or speech, redirecting attention to shared screens or documents.	Goodwin (2000); Dillenbourg (1999) – Scaffolding group coordination and participation repair.

Table 6: Codebook from batch 6.

Code Label	Definition	Representative Behaviors	Theoretical Grounding
Mutual Co-Construction (MCC)	All group members are jointly focused on a shared resource or problem, visibly coordinating actions and attention.	Synchronized gaze at screen or shared artifact; co-occurring gestures (e.g., pointing, nodding); reciprocal body orientation; frequent attention shifts between resource and peers; visible grounding actions.	Goodwin (2000): “co-operative construction of action” through embodiment; Dillenbourg (1999): shared task space and mutuality.
Asymmetric Facilitation (ASF)	One student clearly leads or scaffolds group activity while others participate more passively but attentively.	One student gesturing while others maintain gaze and nod; facilitator frequently shifts gaze between peers and shared screen; listeners leaning in but contributing minimally.	Goodwin (2007): participation frameworks and stance; Dillenbourg (1999): asymmetry in contribution as part of collaboration.

Code Label	Definition	Representative Behaviors	Theoretical Grounding
Parallel Individual Engagement (PIE)	Students are focused on the same or related task but operate independently, with limited interaction or alignment.	Gaze fixed on own laptops/papers; minimal gesturing; upright or slightly slouched postures; rare gaze shifts toward others; shared silence.	Dillenbourg (1999): co-presence without interdependence; Goodwin (2000): lack of “co-operative embodied participation.”
Transitional Alignment (TA)	Students alternate between individual and group work, showing dynamic attention shifts that signal coordination and re-alignment.	Students glance from laptops to peers; brief verbal or gestural exchanges; returning to own work after confirmation or clarification.	Goodwin (2007): stance-taking and reconfiguration of participation; Dillenbourg (1999): fluid transitions in roles and focus.
Peripheral Monitoring (PM)	One or more students observe or monitor group activity without overt engagement, while others lead the task.	Gaze oriented toward active peer but no gestures; passive body language (e.g., arms crossed, leaning back); occasional nodding; minimal speech or tool use.	Goodwin (2000): embodied stance of observer; Dillenbourg (1999): peripheral participants in loosely coupled collaboration.
Disengaged Presence (DP)	One or more students are physically present but not cognitively or socially engaged in the group task.	Gaze fixed on unrelated device (e.g., phone); slouched posture; lack of shared gaze or interaction; minimal task-relevant motion.	Goodwin (2000): misalignment of participation frames; Dillenbourg (1999): breakdown in shared activity structure.

Table 7: Codebook from batch 7.

Label	Definition	Representative Non-Verbal Behaviors	Collaborative Interpretation
Focused Co-Attention	All group members show synchronized visual and bodily orientation toward a shared resource (screen, paper, simulation), with open postures and mutual responsiveness.	Mutual gaze shifts between laptops and peers, aligned bodies facing shared screen, frequent nodding or mirroring, co-speech gestures.	Indicates high-level coordination and mutual commitment to the shared task. Reflects Dillenbourg’s notion of shared cognitive responsibility.
Parallel but Disconnected	Students work side-by-side with individual focus and minimal awareness of others’ contributions or needs.	Downward gazes fixed on own screens or papers, minimal gaze toward peers, no shared gestures or visible alignment.	Resembles parallel play; collaboration potential is latent. Aligns with Goodwin’s view that participation frameworks are not co-constructed here.

Label	Definition	Representative Non-Verbal Behaviors	Collaborative Interpretation
Task-Switching Synchrony	Students exhibit coordinated attention shifts between personal work and group discussion or resources.	Gaze shifts between screen and peer, occasional leaning toward others, nodding or brief eye contact, responsive gestures.	Suggests fluid transitions between individual and collaborative cognitive frames. Embodies Goodwin's concept of "contextual configuration" of action.
Initiative-Driven Discussion	One student leads while others respond nonverbally (e.g., listening, nodding), often orienting toward the speaker or shared material.	Speaker uses hand gestures, frequent gaze to peers; others nod, lean in, or look at shared object as speaker gestures.	Reflects emerging asymmetry in participation roles. Demonstrates Dillenbourg's "collaborative asymmetry" through leader/follower dynamics.
Monitoring Stance	One or more students are engaged in their own tasks but exhibit occasional awareness of peer activity without overt interaction.	Infrequent glance toward peer work, brief gaze shifts, neutral posture, lack of joint orientation.	Indicates passive awareness or readiness for potential collaboration. Embodied stance reflects possible alignment (Goodwin, 2007).
Reflective Contemplation	Individuals or groups display inward-oriented, often stationary postures, marked by minimal movement and reduced interactivity.	Leaning back, head resting on hand, fixed gaze downward, stillness.	Signifies internal processing or fatigue; may be productive (reflection) or signal disengagement.
Joint Problem Space Engagement	Students co-construct meaning through non-verbal coordination around a shared material artifact (e.g., paper or screen).	Simultaneous pointing, mutual gaze at object, shared writing space, back-and-forth gaze or gesture exchanges.	Embodied manifestation of a "joint problem space" (Roschelle & Teasley, 1995, expanded via Goodwin's contextual configuration).
Disengaged Synchrony	Group shows alignment in disengagement: limited gestures, non-expansive posture, prolonged silences or passive stares.	Arms crossed, gazes fixed away from peers or task, minimal interaction, no shifts in posture or focus.	Signals group stagnation or shared confusion. Embodied evidence of collaborative breakdown.

Table 8: Codebook from batch 8.

Code	Definition	Key Behaviors	Theoretical Alignment	Typical Example
Coordinated Co-Attention	All group members are actively engaged with both task and each other. Gaze, gestures, and posture are mutually responsive, indicating shared focus and aligned intentions.	Sustained mutual gaze, co-reference to screen/paper, synchronized gestures, reciprocal nodding, leaning in together.	Goodwin's (2007) participation frameworks; Dillenbourg's co-construction.	Student A points at laptop while Student B types; both nod and look at each other and the screen.
Parallel Individual Engagement	Students are individually focused on the task, working in parallel with minimal interaction, yet showing awareness of others.	Independent gaze on laptops/papers, brief glances at peers, parallel task engagement without coordination.	Dillenbourg's distributed cognition; Goodwin's embodied ecology of action.	Two students silently working on different screens but occasionally glance at each other's paper or screen.
Fragmented Engagement	Group members are inconsistently engaged or misaligned in attention. Gaze and body orientation suggest fragmented or shifting focus across people and tools.	Mixed postures, averted gaze, attention shifts between unrelated focal points, asynchronous behaviors.	Dillenbourg on coordination breakdowns; Goodwin on participation misalignment.	One student on phone, another looking at screen, third trying to initiate eye contact without response.
Asymmetric Collaboration	One student takes a dominant or leader role (gestures, speaks, directs attention), while others take passive or supportive roles.	One student gestures or talks frequently, others nod, gaze at leader, minimal verbal/gestural contribution.	Goodwin's stancetaking; Dillenbourg's script-based interaction roles.	One student explains using gestures while peers nod or write, rarely initiating their own contributions.
Silent Co-Attentive Work	Students exhibit high engagement without overt verbal interaction; non-verbal cues indicate synchronization and mutual awareness.	Shared gaze on screen/paper, simultaneous typing/writing, similar body posture, glances to confirm alignment.	Goodwin (2000) on embodied coordination; Dillenbourg on shared knowledge spaces.	Two students write on paper, glance at shared screen, occasionally exchange glances but no talking.

Code	Definition	Key Behaviors	Theoretical Alignment	Typical Example
Peripheral Participation	One or more students are physically or behaviorally distanced from the group, contributing little or attending passively.	Crossed arms, reclined posture, rare gaze to peers or shared tools, little movement.	Goodwin’s participation frameworks (peripheral vs ratified participants); Dillenbourg on uneven participation.	Two students collaborate while a third sits back, arms crossed, glancing occasionally but not engaging.
Responsive Collaboration-on-Demand	Students primarily work independently but respond promptly to non-verbal or brief verbal cues for momentary collaboration.	Head turns, quick glances, leaning in during partner gestures, brief pointing or shared gaze.	Goodwin’s sequential organization of interaction; Dillenbourg on opportunistic collaboration.	One student leans in and points at the screen; peer immediately looks and adjusts their work.
Focused Individual Work (Non-Collaborative)	All students work silently on individual tasks with no evident collaboration, gaze, or gestural coordination.	Fixed gaze on individual screens, no gestures or glances to peers, no shared focus.	Dillenbourg’s distinction between co-location and collaboration.	Each student types on own laptop, no eye contact, shared materials unused.

Table 9: Codebook from batch 9.

Label	Definition	Theoretical Grounding	Typical Behaviors / Example Segment
Co-Constructive Alignment	Group members actively co-orient toward shared materials through synchronized gaze, gestures, and body alignment. Mutual engagement and embodied reciprocity.	Goodwin (2000): Embodied participation; Dillenbourg (1999): Interdependence of actions	Students lean in, make eye contact, gesture toward screen; mutual tracking (e.g., 21:00–21:10)
Coordinated Multi-tasking	Students divide tasks while maintaining shared awareness through occasional glances and minimal cues. Balanced individual and collective focus.	Goodwin (2007): Participation and stance; Dillenbourg: Division of labor	One student types, another writes; brief glances ensure group alignment (e.g., 22:00–22:10)

Label	Definition	Theoretical Grounding	Typical Behaviors / Example Segment
Peripheral Engagement	One or more students show low interaction and minimal responsiveness to group activities. Limited gaze toward peers or shared materials.	Goodwin (2000): Gradient participation; Dillenbourg: Asymmetry in contributions	One student distracted on phone while peers work; no gestures or mutual gaze (e.g., 27:10–27:20)
Task-Silent Synchrony	Students silently coordinate while focused on the same resource, with minimal interaction. Attention is aligned but not interactive.	Goodwin: Structures of alignment; Dillenbourg: Collaboration without explicit communication	All students look at the same screen or paper; working in silence but in sync (e.g., 31:50–32:00)
Individual Parallelism	Students focus solely on their own tasks, without visible co-orientation. No mutual gaze, shared space, or interaction.	Goodwin: Absence of embodied participation; Dillenbourg: Group \neq collaboration	Students facing laptops, no eye contact, no interaction (e.g., 30:50–31:00)
Emergent Turn-Taking	Students participate sequentially through clear cues like eye contact, nods, or pauses. Speaking and listening roles visibly structured by non-verbal behavior.	Goodwin (2007): Stance and turn-taking; Dillenbourg: Negotiated interaction scripts	One student speaks while others listen and nod; eye contact manages the flow (e.g., 20:40–20:50)
Facilitated Anchoring	One student temporarily leads with verbal/visual input while others anchor their attention on them. The group organizes around a central participant.	Goodwin (2000): Semi-otic fields and anchoring; Dillenbourg: Knowledge asymmetry guiding group dynamics	Student reads from paper, others look up and take notes; group visually aligned to speaker (e.g., 21:00–21:10)

Table 10: Codebook from batch 10.

Label	Definition	Representative Behaviors
Coordinated Co-Engagement	Students are simultaneously engaged in a shared task, coordinating their gaze, gestures, and attention toward joint resources with mutual awareness.	Mutual gaze alternates with shared screen/paper; synchronized leaning in; one gestures while others write or nod; joint attention to Kanban board or simulation interface.
Asymmetrical Contribution	One student leads or explains while others are primarily passive but attentive, showing minimal reciprocal non-verbal feedback or initiative.	One gestures or types while others watch silently; gaze from followers toward leader; nodding without verbal or gestural reciprocation; passive reception of instructions.

Label	Definition	Representative Behaviors
Parallel Individual Engagement	Students work independently in close proximity, showing little to no coordination or shared focus, with attention directed to personal materials.	All gaze at individual screens or papers; no shared gestures or gaze; individual posture (e.g., slightly turned away); absence of interaction or mutual awareness.
Opportunistic Monitoring	Students are mainly focused on individual work but intermittently monitor each other, signaling peripheral awareness without sustained collaboration.	Brief sideways glances at peer's screen; leaning in slightly without speaking; irregular gaze shifts to peer or shared display; subtle signs of attentiveness without overt response.
Distributed Coordination	Students engage in a joint task with differentiated roles, showing complementary actions and attention across various resources.	One types, another gestures, another writes; gaze alternates between peer and screen; role-based participation (e.g., speaker, recorder, navigator); cross-referenced use of tools.
Disengaged or Divergent Focus	One or more students display signs of detachment from the group or task, indicated by divergent gaze, posture, or personal device use.	Head resting on hand, looking away; attention on phone; arms crossed or body turned outward; no eye contact or engagement with group materials; prolonged stillness or distraction.

APPENDIX 4: HUMAN–VIDEO AND HUMAN–GPT CODING

To compare direct MLLM-based coding with the staged MLLM → LLM approach, we used the same finalized codebook and mutually exclusive coding structure in both conditions. Because each video segment could receive only one code, all five codes were presented together in a single prompt, and the model was asked to select the best-fitting code. This design maintained consistency across conditions and helped ensure that differences in results were more likely to reflect differences between direct video-based coding and transcript-based coding rather than differences in prompt structure.

Table 11: Agreement between human coding, direct LLaVA video-based coding, and GPT-4o transcript-based coding.

Code Name	H/V	H/G
Coordinated Collaboration	0.20	0.91
Asymmetric Collaboration	-0.1	0.69
Peripheral Engagement	0	0.63
Parallel Engagement	0	0.65
Disengagement	/	/

Note. H/V refers to agreement between human coding and direct video-based coding by LLaVA. H/G refers to agreement between human coding and GPT-4o coding based on

LLaVA-generated behavioral transcripts. Values report the kappa coefficient (κ) for each code category.

The H/V results showed low agreement between human coding and direct LLaVA video-based coding. In the direct video-coding condition, LLaVA assigned segments to only two categories: *Coordinated Collaboration* and *Asymmetric Collaboration*. It did not assign any segments to *Peripheral Engagement* or *Parallel Engagement*, although these categories appeared in the human-coded data. This pattern suggests that, when applying the finalized codebook directly to video, LLaVA had difficulty distinguishing among the full set of collaboration categories. In contrast, GPT-4o coding based on behavioral transcripts showed higher agreement with human coding across categories.